

Figure 1: The indication of symbolic prosody boundaries.

2.3. Used prosody markers

The labels usually used are;

- M3 for clause boundaries,
- M2 for constituent boundaries likely to be marked prosodically,
- M1 that are close to a M3 boundary and are most certainly not marked prosodically and
- M0 for every other word boundary.

The second class is determined through acoustic perceptual sessions and text is labeled speaker dependent. Acoustic-prosodic boundaries were defined as in Institute of Phonetics (BAS) and used in VERBMOBIL (Kompe, 1997);

- B3 prosodic clause boundary,
- B2 prosodic phrase boundary,
- B9 irregular prosodic boundary, usually hesitation, lengthening and unwanted pauses and
- B0 for every other boundary.

The acoustic prosodic boundaries were determined by listening, visual output and boundary indication from our tool. Also the passages on indicated boundaries were taken into the consideration.

3. Database construction

3.1. Text Corpus

The text corpus consists of 1206 text sentences in Slovenian language (orthography) which equals app. 3 hours of speech. The selection of the text was designed to ensure good coverage of the phones in the language also some clauses gathered from different text styles were included (literature). Other textual factors that might be prosodically important were not considered.

The whole corpus was determined with gathering 31 million words from e-newspapers, e-literature on the WEB or CD's.

Sentences were chosen between 15 and 25 words. 4 different text corpora were generated and statistically

analyzed. After statistically analyzing the text the final corpora was generated. The criteria for final text filtering was based on monophones, diphones, triphones and fivefones richness.

Table 1 : Statistical analysis of phones.

Text corpus	1	2	3	4
Monophones	38	38	38	38
Diphones	1030	1001	1028	1028
Triphones	11398	10233	11283	9126
Fivefones	64811	55218	69668	52039

With the goal not to loose any unit from the corpus only wanting to remove the units duplicates, a careful elimination of sentences considering the unit context was performed. At the end all sentences with duplicated units were removed (Rojc, 2000).

3.2. Audio Recordings

The audio database recordings were created with a male speaker reading aloud isolated sentences sampled at 44.1 KHz (16bit).

3.3. Phonetic transcription

The orthographic transcription was managed with a two step conversion module. The first step is rule-based and the second step is data driven (neural networks were used). The first part was intended for the case were no morphological lexica was available. First rule based stress assignment is done, followed by grapheme-to-phoneme conversion procedure.

The step of stress marking before grapheme-to-phoneme conversion is very important for Slovenian language, since the latter very much depends on the type and place of the stress. In case we have available phonetic lexicon, data driven approach, representing the second part in the module, using neural network can be used. Here, the phonetic lexicon is used as a data source for training the neural networks. The neural network which was taken for the basis of this part is based on a method used and described in SNNS.

The data preparation, the generation of the training patterns and the training of neural networks are done completely automatically. The transcription is performed in two steps. The first one converts the graphemes into phonemes and inserts the syllable breaks in the phoneme string, and the second one inserts stress marks. The problem how to perform mapping between graphemes and phonemes by generation of training patterns for neural network, was solved automatically.

For both neural networks a multilayer perceptron (MLP) feed-forward network with one hidden layer was used. As learning algorithm the back-propagation algorithm was chosen.

The pronunciation is derived from the IPA-Alphabet. In order to represent the IPA symbols in ASCII characters the SAMPA format is widely used. In our grapheme-to-phoneme conversion module the SAMPA phonetic transcription symbols for Slovenian language are used (Rojc, 2000).

3.4. Part of Speech labels

The text corpus was hand labeled using the following simplified Part of Speech markers (POS):

1. SUBST for nouns
2. VERB for verbs
3. ADJ for adjectives
4. ADV for adverbs
5. NUM for ordinal and cardinal numbers
6. PRON for pronouns (noun and adverb)
7. PRED for predicative
8. PREP for prepositions
9. CONJ for conjunctions
10. PART for particle
11. INT for interjection
12. PUNC for punctuation

An example of POS labeled sentence:

Dvesto NUM deset NUM centimetrov SUBST visoki ADJ Nemeč SUBST ne ADV skriva VERB ambicij SUBST v PREP ameriški ADJ ligi SUBS , PUNC saj ADV je VERB tik ADV pred PREP prvenstvom SUBST zavrnil VERB nekaj PRON ponudb SUBST bogatih ADJ evropskih ADJ klubov SUBST . PUNC

3.5. Phonetic segmentation and labeling

The spoken corpus was phonetically transcribed using HTK.

Phone durations

```
#!MLF!#
"/stavek_1.lab"
0 1750000 sil
1750000 2650000 d
2650000 2950000 v
2950000 3900000 e:
3900000 5000000 s
5000000 5250000 t
5250000 5550000 O
5550000 5550000 sp
5550000 6000000 d
6000000 6600000 E
```

First line denotes that this database is an output of HTK. In second line is the name of the file from which was calculated begin and end of phonemes. All other lines point to the beginning and ending of phonemes. First column denotes phoneme beginning, the second phoneme ending in the speech signal file. The third column denotes the name of the phoneme. There are two special markers for pauses between phonemes. "sil" denotes the silence before and after sentence. "sp" denotes the silence between words in the sentence.

3.6. Boundary strength labeling

Yet we used only three labels; B2, B3, B9 as described in preceding paragraphs.

4. A tool for interactive prosody indication

The tool (Figure 1) was intended to make indications of possible prosody boundaries depending on the detected pauses in spoken corpora.

Syllable and word boundaries are line marked adding overview clearness and *B* marks for symbolic prosody boundaries are inserted in the sentence concerned.

Tool inserts marks for symbolic prosody boundaries concerning phonetic segmentation. The position of symbolic prosody boundary is selected where is the silence between words is larger then before selected threshold. This threshold can be changed manually.

Yet we did not implement any boundary strength classification and syntactical prosody labels were not discussed.

4.1. Prosody boundaries labeled text

An example of hand labeled text:

Bojevnika sta po rivalstvu pisno naznanila premirje B3, potem ko sta med B9 rokovanjem v Jerebovi jedilnici pozirala B2 ob ogromnem polnjenem B2 morskem psu B3.

The symbolic labels for acoustic boundaries described in preceding section were used.

An example of semiautomatic labeled text corpora for the same sentence:

Bojevnika sta po rivalstvu pisno naznanila premirje, *B* potem ko sta med *B* rokovanjem v Jerebovi jedilnici pozirala *B* ob ogromnem polnjenem *B* morskem psu.

Yet only breaks with no classification are indicated.

5. Results

The comparison between the semiautomatic and hand-labeled text corpora was done.

Table 2: Comparison between semiautomatic and hand-labeled corpora.

	Number	%
B correct	2779	89,72
B incorrect	0	0
B2 incorrect	260	8,39
B3 incorrect	9	0,29
B9 incorrect	49	1,58
Overall B incorrect	318	10,27
Overall B	3096	

The results are promising in comparison due tests done with other only hand-labeled corpora in Data-Driven Generation of Symbolic Prosody (Müller, 2000).

6. Future work

The phonetic transcription should be additionally handcrafted-checked by an expert minimizing the errors in symbolic boundary detector.

Extending the proposed tool with classification algorithms and adding syntactic prosodic boundaries in classification scheme will be the main topic of our future work. Furthermore adding word prominence labels and finally automatic generation of boundary strength is also our future goal.

The completing of corpora should be done adding word prominence labeled corpus and some tests of importance of non linguistic expertise in POS and prosodic boundary strength labeling should be done. We would like to determine the importance of wrong/right labeling the different POS classes in addition to automatic learning approaches.

7. References

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